

- G.1 **Define the aim of the experiment:** use *Goal-Question-Metric* (GQM) [3]. An example taken from [38]: “The goal of this evaluation was to **analyze** the regression testing approach **for the purpose of evaluation with respect to understandability, usability, completeness, applicability and effectiveness from the point of view of SPL researchers and test engineers in the context of an SPL project.**”
- G.2 **State the hypotheses of the experiment:** establish null hypothesis and alternative hypotheses, as proposed in [42]. The following example is from [32]:
- “**Null Hypothesis H0:** The representativeness is the same, when using the *Odyssey-Fex* or *UI-Odyssey-Fex* notations, to represent UI elements.”
 - “**Alternative Hypothesis H1:** The use of the *UI-Odyssey-Fex* notation better represents UI elements when compared with the *Odyssey-Fex* notation.”
- G.3 **Define the variables of the experiment:** establish independent and dependent variables [42]. The example given below was taken from [30]: “The **independent variable** in this case was familiarity with feature modeling, while the **dependent variables** were comprehension scores (measured using the percentage of correct solution), time spent to complete tasks, and difficulty perception using self-rated difficulty of specific element types.”
- G.4 **Inform the sample size:** 1) for human subjects, it is essential to inform the size of the sample, because size can be a threat to the experiment; and 2) for algorithms/software, inform the number of executions performed. Examples are from [33] and [25], respectively:
1. “Nineteen senior undergraduate students enrolled in a Software Engineering course acted as subjects.”
 2. “We executed 30 independent runs for each feature model input set for each of the three algorithms and for each objective function. The total number of independent runs is thus: $74(\text{feature models}) \times 3(\text{algorithms}) \times 2(\text{objective functions}) \times 30 \text{ runs} = 13,320.$ ”
- G.5 **Describe how participants/experimental objects were selected:** 1) important information to be described in the case of human participants are their characterization, including, for instance, the type (student or professionals), recruitment (voluntary or mandatory), background (e.g., academic degree), and experience in relevant tasks (e.g., programming skills); 2) regarding experimental objects of experiments that are not performed by human participants, but with algorithms, this includes if the algorithm used was developed by the authors or was taken from the literature, if the source code is available for download and the configurations of the machine and parameters to run it, for example; and 3) describe their selection in relation to the chosen sampling technique proposed by Wohlin et al. [42], such as: Simple random sampling, Systematic sampling, Stratified random sampling, Convenience sampling, and Quota sampling. Examples for cases 1 and 3 were taken from [38] and 2 from [23] and [25], respectively:
1. and 3. “This evaluation involved eight participants. All of them had completed a post-graduate course in the software testing area prior to this evaluation. The subjects were either upper-level computer science majors or graduate students. They were selected by convenience sampling, which means that the nearest and most convenient persons were selected as participants [13] (...)”
 2. “In this paper, we designed MOOFHD and MOOF ϵ + by introducing our SolutionRevise operator into IBEA suggested by [6]. Our two algorithms with NSGAI[8], SPEA2[9], IBEAHD[10] and IBEA ϵ + [10] were experimented on the four models. All of these algorithms were implemented in jMetal[11], a popular framework for multi-objective optimization. The parameters of these algorithms are default values in jMetal: population size=100, single-point crossover, crossover probability=0.90, bit-flip mutation, mutation probability=1/NumberOfVariables.”
 2. “We ran our experiments on an array of different machines with 4-16 cores with clock speeds between 2 and 4 GHz with 4-16 GBs of memory.”
- G.6 **Identify the research topic of the experiment:** the mind map of research topics investigated in the SPL experiments identified in the SMS can be used to aid in the identification. The mind map that supports the guidelines is available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3893302>. The following example was elaborated by the authors based on the mind map: “The experiment was conducted in the research topic of regression testing in product line architecture.”
- G.7 **Describe the chosen experimental design:** it is necessary to know if the experiment is able to adequately test the hypotheses, thus using the general experimental design principles proposed by Wohlin et al. [42], such as: blocking, randomization, and balancing. Depending on the experimental context a design may have specific arrangements, such as: one factor with two treatments, one factor with more than two treatments, two factors with two treatments, and more than two factors each two treatments. In addition, it is important to describe how groups, objects, tasks, and treatments relate. An example taken from [26] is presented below: “One factor with two treatments. We compared the two treatments against each other [16]. Factor in this experiment was the RiPLE-TE unit testing process and treatments were: (1) Testing with the process; and (2) testing without it (...)”
- G.8 **Describe how the experimental materials were defined and selected:** there are three types of experimental materials: objects (specifications or code documents); guidelines (process descriptions and checklists); and measurement instruments (performed by data collection such as interviews and manual forms), according to Wohlin et al. [42]. For example, inform the size of materials, the tools used. To illustrate this guideline, an example was taken from [26]: “Objects used in this experiment was as follows: Consent Form, Background Questionnaire, Test Assets and Component Source Code, RiPLE-TE Documentation - including guidelines and usage samples, Error Reporting Form, Feedback Questionnaire (...)”
- G.8.1 **Describe the SPL used:** it is important to present the description of the SPL used in experiment, besides its name. An example taken from [9] is given below: “To validate our approach, we have applied it to a collection of seven variants

of a large-scale system, ArgoUML-SPL modeling tool, and five variants of a small-scale system, MobileMedia. The ArgoUML-SPL is a Java open-source which supports all standard UML 1.4 diagrams (...)

- G.8.1.1 **Inform the source where the SPL was found:** if available, it is important to present the source, either from the literature or from a website, to enable future replication, for example. Ideally, such information should be included in the replication package. The example below is from [23]: “Four feature models including two realistic models and two synthesis were selected from SPLLOT[7], a popular feature model repository.”
- G.8.2 **Describe the SPL artifacts used in the experiment:** the mind map of SPL artifacts identified in SMS can be used to assist in their selection. The mind map that supports the guidelines can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3893302>. The following example is taken from [30]: “The objects of the experiment were two CVL models describing different sets of features of Skoda Yeti cars. The CVL models for the experiment were built by Prof. Haugen, who is the founder of CVL and is familiar with the possible Skoda Yeti configurations from the Norwegian Skoda public web pages (...)”
- G.9 **Validate the materials used in the experiment:** validate materials used such as questionnaires, forms, and interviews to verify reliability and provide insight into the type of knowledge requested by the experiment. One technique that can support such validation for questionnaires is Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [13].
- G.10 **Describe the tasks of the experiment:** describe the tasks to be performed by participants with a level of detail to enable replication without the need to consult the authors of original experiment. If possible, provide the duration and schedule to perform such tasks. An example of [33] is presented below: “In the tasks, the subjects had to find the code of both, modular (when the feature is implemented in a single file or in set of files placed together) and scattered (when the code of a single feature is spread over several source files) features (...)”
- G.11 **Describe the training requirements for participants:** it is necessary to provide appropriate training to participants in all treatment conditions. The example shown below was taken from [38]: “The subjects were trained in several aspects of SPL, and control flow graphs, besides the use of the following tools: Junit(<http://www.junit.org/>), EclEmma plugin(<http://www.eclEmma.org/>), and JDiff tool [5]. The analyzed approach was also another training topic. Next, they performed the regression testing approach in the code provided (...)”
- G.12 **Describe the conduct of the pilot study:** it is suggested to carry out a pilot study, which is a simplified version of experiment, to evaluate materials and experimental design, for example. In addition, it is suggested to apply the pilot study to evaluate the materials to experts in the area. Such a guideline is illustrated by the example of [38] below: “Before performing the evaluation, two pilot projects were conducted with the same structure defined in this planning phase. The first pilot was performed by a single subject, aiming to detect problems and calibrate the evaluation process before its real execution (...)”
- G.13 **Describe the environment for conducting the experiment:** inform if the experiment was conducted in an academic or industrial environment, for example. Below is an example taken from [2]: “The experiment was executed at Simon Fraser University (...)”
- G.14 **Inform the date the experiment was performed:** it is important to inform the date the experiment was performed, because it may take some time for the experiment to be published. The following is the example of [26]: “The experiment was conducted from November to December in 2009, according to the definition and planning documented.”
- G.15 **Describe the conduct of experiment:** it is necessary to describe how the experiment was carried out to allow its replication, including the preparation of materials and participants/objects. Also, report any changes in the execution and schedule of experiment. Such advice is illustrated with an example taken from [37]: “The experiment was performed using a set of eight subjects, where each one applied the approach in both scenarios. Firstly, both code versions were provided with a set of change requests (three), as well as a set of previously designed integration test cases, for the subjects to validate the approach considering the corrective scenario. The subjects needed to apply the approach aiming to find the seeded faults, as well as to classify the integration test cases (...)”
- G.16 **Describe how the data collection was performed:** data collection can be performed manually or through specific tools, data sources may involve task outcomes, log files, among others. An example of [38] is shown below: “The results of the evaluation were collected using measurement instruments. Thus, time-sheets were used to collect the time spent in each activity (...)”
- G.17 **Describe the procedures for analyzing the collected data:** to analyze the collected data one can use descriptive statistics, normality tests, parametric or non-parametric hypothesis tests and correlations, for example. In addition, it is important to justify the choice and provide references to the descriptions of procedures. The examples of descriptive statistics and hypothesis testing were taken from [26], as shown below:
- “**Test case effectiveness.** In terms of valid defects found, in group 1 (G-1) (without run the process), the mean value was 6.188 with an standard deviation (sd) of 3.187, while in group 2 (G-2) (with the process), the mean was 3.857, with a sd of 3.505 (...)”
 - “**Hypothesis Testing.** Regarding TCE, t-test (unpaired, two-tailed) was applied and resulted in a p-value higher than 0.05, which indicates that the Null Hypothesis H01 could not be rejected. H02 could not also be rejected, since calculated p-value was higher than 0.05.”
- G.18 **Describe the mortality rate:** there are two types of sample size: the initial number of participants or executions and the number of participants or executions included in the analysis of data. Thus, describe both numbers, as well as the reasons for drop outs or exclusions. An example of [38] is

shown below: “*Corrective Scenario: Table II shows the raw data collected after the experiment execution, where “not considered (NC)” means that the step was not reported correctly and “not reported (NR)” means that no time was reported by the subject. Before analyzing the collected data, some issues were observed: Test Design and Test Selection steps needed to be refined, subjects ID 1 and 3 were removed from the analysis since they did not correctly report the data regarding to this item (...)*”

- G.19 **Inform the statistical tool for data analysis:** it is important to inform the statistical tool used in data analysis, whether or not it is free to there are no divergences in the results when replicating the experiment in another sample. The example given below was taken from [32]: “*We performed hypothesis testing for all data sets using the R Studio statistical environment for R [12].*”
- G.20 **Inform the effect size:** effect size is a technique to check for gain in experimental group. In addition, the hypothesis test can be supported by the effect size. Such a guideline is illustrated with an example of [25]: “*Even when differences in the performance of the algorithms are statistically significant as in our case, it is also crucial to assess the magnitude of such a difference, in order to ensure that such difference has practical value. Following the guidelines provided in (Arcuri and Briand, 2014), we use Vargha and Delaney’s \hat{A}_{12} statistic to evaluate the effect size. Specifically, \hat{A}_{12} measures the probability that using one algorithm yields higher values than the other for a comparison metric (...)*”
- G.21 **Discuss the results obtained from the point of view of researchers and practitioners:** it is necessary the results obtained are also discussed for industry practitioners to be able to identify whether the experiment has practical relevance.
- G.22 **Discuss the implications of treatments developed:** when the treatments were developed it is necessary to discuss the implications of treatments, in order to mitigate their related threats to validity.
- G.23 **Discuss the threats to validity identified in experiment:** Discuss the threats to validity in internal, external, construct, and conclusion, as proposed by Wohlin et al. [42]. An example taken from [33] is shown below:

- “**External validity:** *We identified some threats that may limit the ability to generalize the results. For example, the study was carried out in an in-vitro setting, which means a sample selected pseudo-randomly (...)*”
- “**Internal validity:** *There are possible threats that may happen without the researcher’s knowledge affecting individuals from different perspectives, such as (i) the maturation and learning effects, (ii) the testing repetition since several tasks were carried out, and (iii) the experiment instrumentation. These threats were mitigated by choosing different features for each task, as well as by randomizing the sequence of task’s execution to omit possible relationships (...)*”
- “**Construct Validity:** *Confounding constructs may affect the findings. For instance, the presence or the absence of knowledge about a particular programming language may*

not explain the causes of failures in the feature location tasks. In fact, the differences may depend on the subjects’ experience, which was controlled with the characterization form, to ensure that subjects had substantial experience to accomplish the tasks.”

- “**Conclusion Validity:** *We observed from the results a likely low statistical power, which concerns to the power of used tests to reveal a true pattern in the data. Employing well-known measures mitigated such a threat. Another observed threat is the fishing for a specific result, which we mitigated by relying the analysis only on the gathered data (...)*”

G.24 **Inform the source of experimental package:** The experimental package contains experimental materials, raw data and data analysis scripts, for example. Thus, it is important to present the permanent and public source of the experimental package to enable auditing or future replication, using repositories such as Zenodo, for example. Such a guideline is illustrated below with an example of [31] (although a permanent source would be preferred): “*All data, materials, tasks, plug-ins, and R scripts are available at <http://twiki.cin.ufpe.br/twiki/bin/view/SPG/EmergentInterfaces>.*”

G.25 **Inform the experimental guidance used to conduct, plan or report the experiment:** examples of experimental guidance found in the SMS were: Jedlitschka et al. [12]; Kitchenham et al. [20]; Kitchenham et al. [16]; Sjöberg et al. [39]; and Wohlin et al. [41]. The following is an example taken from [34]: “*The experimental study was based on the process proposed by Wohlin [11].*”